

Some Selective Metal-Halogen Exchange Reactions of Perchloro(2-phenylthiophene)

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Metal-halogen exchange reactions of perchloro-(2-phenylthiophene) with *n*-butyllithium in THF give mono- and dilithium reagents in good yields. Metathesis of the dilithium reagent with copper(I) iodide gives 2-(1-cuprio-2,3,5,6-tetrachlorophenyl)-3,4-dichloro-5-thienylcopper in high yield. Some derivatives of these organometallics are reported.

Magnesium reacts preferentially at the benzene part of perchloro(2-phenylthiophene) in THF giving 1-(trichloro-2-thienyl)-2,3,5,6-tetrachlorophenyl-magnesium chloride (37%).

IN extension of studies on polyhaloarylmetallic compounds¹⁻³, a need arose for the selective introduction of metals by halogen-metal exchange reactions in unsymmetrical perchlorobiaryl types such as 2-(pentachlorophenyl)trichlorothiophene(I). It has been found that preferential exchange reactions can be effected using *n*-butyllithium or magnesium.

Experimental

The general conditions for organometallic reactions, equipment and materials used, were as described previously¹⁻³. All temperatures quoted are uncorrected. The yields of various compounds are based on the starting amount of I.

Preparation of 2-(pentachlorophenyl)-3,4-dichloro-5-thienyllithium, VII: To I (2.3 m moles) in THF (100 ml) at -78° was added dropwise *n*-butyllithium (4.6 m moles) over a period of 10 min and the mixture was stirred for 5 hr. Colour Tests I⁴ and II⁵ were both positive. Eicosane, 1.0038 g (internal standard for glc) in benzene (50 ml) was added and the mixture was then stirred for 15 min. An aliquot was hydrolysed with dil. hydrochloric acid, and the hydrolysate was extracted with benzene. The benzene extract when analysed by glc showed that II and IV were present in 76 and 24% yields, respectively. No other isomer of II and IV were detected. The reaction mixture was stirred for an additional one-hour period, but there was no apparent change in the product distribution.

The other variations of this experiment are given in the table. For the purpose of comparison, II¹ and IV⁶ have been prepared by coupling 3,4-dichloro-2-thienylcopper¹ with pentachloroiodobenzene and 2,3,5,6-tetrachloroiodobenzene, respectively. Similarly III was prepared from trichloro-2-thienylcopper⁷ and 2,3,5,6-tetrachloroiodobenzene⁸,

and I from trichloro-2-thienylcopper and pentachloroiodobenzene[†].

Preparation of 2-(1-lithio-2,3,5,6-tetrachlorophenyl)-3,4-dichloro-5-thienyllithium, VI and its disilyl derivative, VIII: To I (9.2 m moles) in THF (200 ml) at -78° was added slowly *n*-butyllithium (27.6 m moles) over a period of 30 min and the mixture was stirred for 9 hr. An excess of chlorodimethylhydrosilane was added. The mixture was stirred for 1 hr at -78° and then it was allowed to warm slowly to room temperature. Colour Test I⁴ became negative during this time. The mixture was hydrolysed with dil. hydrochloric acid, extracted in benzene; the benzene extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the solvent distilled to give a pale brownish liquid (4.3 g). The liquid was particularly non-volatile and no crystalline material was obtained from it. Upon chromatography through a Silica Gel column using Skelly B as eluant there was obtained 3.14 g, 67% of a highly viscous colourless liquid. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₄Cl₆SSi₂(VIII): Si, 44.02%; found: Si, 43.97%. The ir spectrum showed the following absorption bands in cm⁻¹: 2941, 2907 (C-H); 2174, 2146 (Si-H); 1550, 1530, 1429, 1392, 1290, 1250, 1208, 1130, 1047, 1005, and very broad peaks in the regions 920-834, 780-760 and 730-700. The ¹H nmr spectrum showed three multiplets around δ : 5.15, 4.65 (Si-H) and 0.55 (Si-CH₃) in the integrated ratio of 1:1:12 as expected for VIII. The bis-silyl compound has relatively high thermal stability.

Preparation of 2-(1-cuprio-2,3,5,6-tetrachlorophenyl)-3,4-dichloro-5-thienylcopper reagent, IX and its diacetyl derivative, X: To VI, prepared from 6.9 m moles of I and *n*-butyllithium (20.7 m moles), was added freshly purified anhydrous copper(I) chloride (22 m moles) and the mixture stirred at -78° for

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† As described in *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 299 (M. T. Rahman & H. Gilman).

16 hr. Colour Test I was negative within 12 hr. The mixture was brought to 0° and acetyl chloride (22 m moles) was added. The mixture was stirred for 4 hr. Customary work-up^{1,8} gave a brownish solid (2.3 g, 74%) which, when chromatographed through a Silica Gel column using Skelly B as eluant and subsequently recrystallised from Skelly B, gave a white solid 1.96 g (63%), m.p. 158.5-160°. Calc. for C₁₄H₆Cl₆O₂S (X): Cl, 47.17%; Found Cl, 47.33%. The ir spectrum had the following absorption frequencies in cm⁻¹: 1742, 1653 (-CO-) 1389, 1376, 1361, 1351, 1258, 1190, 1100, 1056 (polychlorinated benzene and thiophene nuclei); 820, 717, 703, 689 and 661 (C-Cl). The ¹Hnmr spectrum showed two singlets at δ: 2.72 and 2.30 (CH₃CO-) in the expected integrated ratio for X.

Reaction of I with Metallic Magnesium: A mixture of I (1.15 m moles), magnesium (20 mg-atoms) and a drop of ethylene bromide in THF (30 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 5 hr. A clear brown solution was obtained. The unreacted magnesium was settled out. The solution gave a faintly positive Colour Test I. The mixture was hydrolysed with dil. hydrochloric acid and the products were estimated as before by glc using eicosane as an internal standard. The compounds II, III and IV were present in 3, 37 and 4% yields. Approximately 50% of I was recovered from this reaction.

Results and Discussion

Perchloro(2-phenylthiophene) (I) reacts with one equivalent of *n*-butyllithium in THF to give, subsequent to hydrolysis, 2-pentachlorophenyl-3,4-dichlorothiophene (II, 47%), 2-(2, 3, 5, 6-tetrachlorophenyl) trichlorothiophene (III, 14%), and 2-(2, 3, 5, 6-tetrachlorophenyl)-3,4-dichlorothiophene (IV, 16%), and 20% of I was recovered. The product distribution indicates that the α-position of the thiophene nucleus of I is the most reactive position of this compound for metal-halogen exchange reactions with *n*-butyllithium.

When two equivalents of *n*-butyllithium were used under similar conditions, II and IV were formed in 76 and 24% yields, respectively (Table 1).

The good yield of II and the absence of III indicate that once V is formed it reacts more rapidly than VII with a second molecule of butyllithium to give the dilithio compound VI.

When three equivalents of *n*-butyllithium were used, I gave the dilithio compound VI as the major product (77%). Only a small amount (3%) of VII remained as a contaminant of the dilithio reagent. The halogen-metal exchange reaction also occurs in ether and ether-benzene but to a lesser extent.

- I, R=R'=Cl
 II, R=Cl, R'=H
 III, R=H, R'=Cl
 IV, R=R'=H
 V, R=Li, R'=Cl
 VI, R=R'=Li
 VII, R=Cl, R'=Li
 VIII, R=R'=SiMe₂H
 IX, R=R'=Cu
 X, R=R'=CH₃CO-
 XI, R=MgCl, R'=Cl

The dilithium reagent, VI reacts with chlorodimethylhydrosilane to give the bis-silylated product, VIII in 67% yield. Metathesis of VI with copper(I) chloride in THF gives the corresponding di-copper reagent, IX. The formation of IX was indicated by a negative Colour Test I⁴ and by its reaction^{7,8} with acetyl chloride to give the diketone, X (63%).

The reaction of I with metallic magnesium has not been explored extensively. Preliminary experiments indicated that the 4-position of the benzene ring is the most reactive centre, and a yield of at least 37% of the Grignard reagent, XI was obtained. This is in contrast to the lithiation of I by *n*-butyllithium when VII is formed preferentially. The proximity of a hetero-atom may make the γ-position of the thiophene part more reactive for metal-halogen exchange than the 4-position of the benzene part⁹.

TABLE 1—SOME HALOGEN-METAL EXCHANGE REACTIONS OF PERCHLORO(2-PHENYLTHIOPHENE), I

I m moles	Solvent, ml	Temp °C	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉ Li m moles	Period of addn. min	Reactn. time hr	Products*, %yield**			Recovery of I, %
						II	III	IV	
2.30	THF, 100	-78	2.30	15	3	47	14	16	20
2.30	THF, 100	-78	4.60	10	5	76	nil	24	nil
2.30	Et ₂ O, 100	-15	2.30	15	3	6	13	25	50
2.30	Et ₂ O-PhH†	-15	2.60	15	5	22	25	23	26
1.15	THF, 80	-78	3.45	10	9	3	nil	77	nil

* Subsequent to acid hydrolysis. Analysed by GLC using eicosane as an internal standard.

** Based on the starting amount of I.

† An 1 : 1 mixture, 150 ml.

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